

Gut Microbiota-Related Biomarkers in Immuno-oncology

Carolina Alves Costa Silva*^{1,2}, Marine Fidelle*^{1,2}, Andrew A. Almonte*^{1,2}, Lisa Derosa†^{1,2,3}, Laurence Zitvogel†^{1,2,3,4#}

Affiliations :

¹ Gustave Roussy Cancer Campus (GRCC), Clinicobiome, Villejuif Cedex, France

² Institut National de la Santé Et de la Recherche Médicale (INSERM) U1015, Equipe Labellisée—Ligue Nationale contre le Cancer, Villejuif, France.

³ Faculté de Médecine, Université Paris-Saclay, Kremlin-Bicêtre, France.

⁴ Center of Clinical Investigations BIOTHERIS, INSERM CIC1428, Villejuif, France.

*These authors contributed equally

†These authors jointly supervised this work.

#Corresponding author: laurence.zitvogel@gustaveroussy.fr (L.Zi.)

Gustave Roussy, 114 rue Edouard Vaillant, 94805 Villejuif Cedex France

ORCID 0000-0003-1596-0998 (L.Zi.)

Abstract

Carcinogenesis is associated with the emergence of protracted intestinal dysbiosis and metabolic changes. Increasing evidence shows that gut microbiota-related biomarkers and microbiota-centered interventions are promising strategies to overcome resistance to immunotherapy. However, current standard methods for evaluating gut microbiota composition are cost- and time-consuming. The development of routine diagnostic tools for intestinal barrier alterations and dysbiosis constitutes a critical unmet medical need that can guide routine treatment and microbiota-centered interventions decisions in patients with cancer. In this review, we explore the influence of gut microbiota on cancer immunotherapy and highlight gut-associated biomarkers that have the potential to be transformed into simple diagnostic tools, thus guiding standard treatment decisions in the field of immuno-oncology. Mechanistic insights towards leveraging the complex relationship between cancer immunosurveillance, gut microbiota, and metabolism open exciting opportunities for developing novel biomarkers in immuno-oncology.

Keywords

Cancer; Gut; Immunotherapy; Microbiota; Biomarkers; Immuno-Oncology;

Abbreviations

Adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK); Chimeric antigen receptor T cell (CAR-T); Colorectal cancer (CRC); Complete response (CR); Dendritic cells (DC); Deoxycholic acid; Desaminotyrosine (DAT); Endothelial cells (EC); Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT); Gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS); G-alpha interacting vesicle-associated protein or Girdin (GIV); Gut microbiota (GM); High endothelial venules (HEVs); Immune-checkpoint blockade (ICB); Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD); Intestinal fatty acid-binding protein (iFABPs); Lipocalin-2 (LCN2); Lipopolysaccharide (LPS); Lipopolysaccharide-binding protein (LBP); Liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS); Lithocholic acid (LCA); Mesenteric lymph node (mLN); Metagenomics shotgun sequencing (MGS); Microbiota-centered interventions (MCIs); Mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule 1 (MAdCAM-1); Natural killer (NK); Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC); Osteopontin (OPN); Partial response (PR); Plasmalemma vesicle-associated protein-1 (PV-1); Regulatory T cells (Tregs); Renal cell carcinoma (RCC); Secreted phosphoprotein

1 (SPP1); Secretory immunoglobulin A (sIgA); Soluble CD14 (sCD14); Soluble Mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule 1 (sMAdCAM-1); Soluble ST2 (sST2 or sIL33R); Stress polarity signalling (SPS); T helper 17 (Th17); Tertiary lymphoid structures (TLS); Tumor draining lymph node (tdLN); Tumor microenvironment (TME); Type I interferon (IFN-I); Volatile organic compounds (VOCs); Whole-genome sequencing (WGS); 16S rRNA gene sequencing (16S rRNA-seq).

1. Introduction

Cancer and cardiovascular diseases have superseded infectious diseases and became the leading causes of death worldwide in the second half of the 20th century (1). Additionally, we have observed a trend of younger individuals developing cancer at an increased rate (2). Fortunately, the increasing global burden of cancer is accompanied by advances in cancer therapy (3). Oncologic drugs have evolved from cytotoxic compounds and nonspecific immune cytokines to more precision-based modalities such as monoclonal immune checkpoint blockade (ICB) antibodies, which have revolutionized cancer treatment. Over the past decade, immunotherapeutic strategies, especially ICB, have become the backbone of cancer treatment for multiple malignancies across various stages (3). ICB has revolutionized cancer treatment. However, while some patients exhibit durable, lasting responses, only a subset respond to this therapy.

Together with immune checkpoints, other intrinsic and extrinsic factors such as genetics, exposure to sunlight, infectious agents, microbiota, and pharmacological agents interact to determine an individual's 'cancer-immune set point', which is the equilibrium between factors that enhance or suppress anticancer immunity (4, 5). Increasing evidence has also highlighted the important roles that the physiology of the intestinal barrier and the microbiota composition play in cancer immunosurveillance, leading to their inclusion in the emerging Hallmarks of Cancer (4, 6). The potential to modulate the microbiota to shape immune homeostasis led to the identification of gut microbiota (GM)-related biomarkers and the development of microbiota-centered interventions (MCIs) as promising strategies to improve outcomes for patients treated with ICB. MCIs are GM-modulating therapies such as fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT), live biotherapeutic products, prebiotics, diet, and co-medications, all aiming to restore a healthier and more immunogenic gut flora (7). Conditioning of the immune system by an MCI may improve the efficacy of anticancer treatments. Indeed, pilot clinical trials have already demonstrated evidence of the feasibility, safety, and efficacy of FMT in non-selected patients (8–12).

In this review, we describe the impact of GM in cancer immunotherapy and identify developing gut-related biomarkers that can be translated into simple diagnostic tools to guide routine treatment decisions in immuno-oncology practice. First, we discuss the rationale for designing biomarkers of response to ICB based on the microbiota. Then, we list potential gut-related biomarkers – specifically fecal metagenomics, gut barrier-related markers, lymphocyte responses to commensals and microbial-derived metabolites that can help caregivers make better-informed decisions about who derives the most benefit from MCIs together with ICB treatments (Figure 1).

2. Rationale of designing biomarkers of response to ICB based on the microbiota

The microbiota is a dynamic community of bacteria, archaea, viruses, fungi, and protozoa within the gastrointestinal tract (13). In this review, we focus on the bacterial domain since it represents the bulk of the GM biomass. The bacterial density increases longitudinally through the gastrointestinal tract, reaching an estimated number of approximately 10^{13} - 10^{14} bacteria inhabiting the adult colon (14). Bacteroidetes, Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, and Proteobacteria constitute the dominant bacteria phyla in the human GM (15, 16). However, the exact proportions of bacterial taxa that colonize the gut can vary significantly across human cultures (intimately linked with diet), lifestyles, and health status (17). The GM also provides several important roles, including acting as a barrier that protects the host from exogenous pathogenic infection, regulating innate and adaptive immune homeostasis, and affecting a host's predisposition to inflammatory diseases (18, 19). This is

accomplished by influencing the development and differentiation of the local mucosal immune system, such as antigen-presenting cells, regulatory T cells (Tregs), T helper 17 (Th17) cells, mucosal IgA B-cell responses, and innate lymphoid cells (18). Indeed, the disruption of gut homeostasis (gut dysbiosis) can lead to a higher risk of proinflammatory states and diseases.

The GM composition of a given individual is primarily explained by environmental factors rather than heritability and genetics (20–23). For example, aging has been associated with deviations in GM composition and function, further highlighting differences between so-called “unhealthy” versus “healthy” aging (24–28). Comedications such as antibiotics, proton pump inhibitors, osmotic laxatives, anti-inflammatory drugs, and biguanide antidiabetics are also examples of environmental factors that can influence GM composition (20, 29–31). Importantly, several studies have repeatedly demonstrated that gut dysbiosis resulting from broad-spectrum antibiotics compromises the efficacy of immunotherapies such as ICB, chimeric antigen receptor T cell (CAR-T) cell therapy, and hematopoietic stem cell transplantation across multiple solid and hematological malignancies (32–41). Curiously, the most significant deleterious effect of antibiotics on ICB therapeutic outcomes is observed among patients who had taken antibiotics between 60 days before (HR 2.26; 95% CI 1.76–2.90) treatment, but the effect lasted until 42 days after they started ICB treatments (7).

The GM can exert not only local (i.e., metabolism, mucosal inflammation and immunity) but also extraintestinal (i.e., microbe translocation, microbial-derived metabolites, endocrine molecules) effects (42). The main mechanisms are related to maintaining gut barrier integrity, maintaining metabolic and endocrine functions, and shaping immunity. Antibiotics affect GM diversity and composition, leading to gut dysbiosis dominated by distinct tolerogenic bacteria, notably *Enterocloster* spp (31, 43, 44). Fidelle et al. discovered that antibiotics-derived gut dysbiosis and subsequent increase in relative *Enterocloster* spp. levels downregulates ileal mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule 1 (MAdCAM-1) expression, an important high endothelial venule molecule involved in gut-homing for $\alpha 4\beta 7$ -expressing leukocytes (43, 45). This down-regulation leads to the recirculation of immunosuppressive enterotropic T cells that eventually accumulate in the tumor bed, thus promoting tumor progression and resistance to ICB treatment in mouse models (43). FMT with appropriate bacterial composition (i.e. devoid of *Enterocloster* spp.), or the administration of the bacterium *Akkermansia muciniphila* alone in dysbiotic mice was sufficient to restore the intestinal expression of MAdCAM-1 to physiological levels (43). These results pave the way to the relative success of pioneering clinical trials using FMT or probiotics in cancer patients (8–10).

Microbial translocation is another mechanism by which GM affects cancer immunosurveillance because the migration of microbes into tumors induces antitumor immunity and increases ICB efficacy (46, 47). How they migrate from the gut to the tumor without triggering a systemic immune reaction is still under investigation. However, Choi et al. used mouse models to demonstrate that dendritic cells (DC) can act as “Trojan horses” by transporting gut microbes into mesenteric lymph nodes (mLN) (46). Furthermore, antibiotics decreased DC-mediated microbial translocation to the mLN and tumor-draining lymph node (tdLN), thus leading to an immunosuppressive phenotype (46).

The profound effect of GM on systemic immunity and cancer therapy responses, and our relative increasing understanding of the underlying mechanisms, open up avenues to effectively manipulate the GM to improve therapy outcome. Defining optimal GM compositions that help prevent disease or are suitable for improving therapy effectiveness is an unmet medical need.

3. Fecal metagenomics

Gut dysbiosis – an imbalance in the GM composition – has been associated with intestinal and extraintestinal cancers. Lower richness of gut microbial genes (microbial diversity) is associated with proinflammatory states and cancer progression (38, 48, 49). Yonekura et al. demonstrated that carcinogenesis induces a “stress ileopathy”, which is defined by an imbalance between sympathetic over cholinergic signalling and a transient modification of the villus/crypt ratio (44). This results in persistent intestinal dysbiosis dominated by tolerogenic *Enterocloster* spp. that participates in cancer

progression and promotes resistance to ICB (44). Indeed, GM composition at the start of ICB differs between patients who benefit from therapy versus those who are resistant to treatment (31, 38, 50–56). Notably, those that respond greatly to ICB tend to have a reduction in tolerogenic *Enterocloster* spp (57). In contrast, the presence of immunogenic bacteria such as *Akkermansia muciniphila*, or species in the *Ruminococcus* or *Bifidobacterium* genera, is associated with improved clinical responses to ICB and increased systemic immune tonus in patient-derived avator mouse models and patients (31, 38, 49, 54, 58, 59). Multiple studies converged on the concept of cancer-related GM signatures. Across various cancer subtypes, patients share a common GM composition different from healthy people (44, 58). A meta-analysis of the GM composition established by metagenomics shotgun sequencing (MGS) of stools highlighted bacterial species associated with cancer, as well as with response or resistance to ICB across diverse cancer types (55).

There is a growing interest in determining the fecal microbial composition of a patient at baseline to assess their propensity to benefit from ICB (predictive value) or to determine their prognosis (prognostic value). Fecal sampling can be easily done at home with proper collection procedures, (60, 61). Current technologies aimed at profiling GM composition rely on MGS, 16S rRNA gene sequencing (16S rRNA-seq), quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR) assays, and sometimes more tedious methods such as culturomics and multiparametric flow cytometry.

While distinct genera and bacterial species are significantly associated with clinical outcomes, the stability of this taxonomic profile varies across studies conducted worldwide (Table 1). These differences can be due to confounding factors such as geographical or cultural specificities, the clinical readout used to translate clinical benefit and other technical factors associated with feces handling or DNA sequencing (7, 20). Further evidence showed that these cancer-related GM signatures are not cancer-specific as different chronic inflammatory disorders share similar deviations from the healthy GM repertoire (i.e., cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders, inflammatory bowel diseases, neurodegenerative disorders, unhealthy ageing) (20). Indeed, *Enterocloster* species, oral taxa (including Streptococcaceae, Veillonellaceae, Actinomyces, Fusobacteriaceae family members), Proteobacteria class, *Anaerotruncus* spp, *Bacteroidia*, *Flavonifractor* spp, *Eggerthellaceae* family members are part of the microbial signatures shared among all chronic inflammatory disorders. In contrast, Lachnospiraceae, Ruminococcaceae and Oscillispiraceae families (including *Faecalibacterium* spp., *Bifidobacterium* spp., *Subdoligranulum* spp., *Oxalobacter*, *Eubacterium* spp, and *Roseburia* spp.) were associated with self-reported positive health status in a three-generational cohort comprising 8208 individuals in the Netherlands (20) as well responses to ICB ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷.

3.1 Single microbial species

The presence of fecal *A. muciniphila* at the start of ICB therapy is associated with favorable clinical outcomes in patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and renal cell carcinoma (RCC) (38, 62). In a prospective validation of the prognostic value of *A. muciniphila* (N=338), Derosa et al. demonstrated that the trichotomization of its relative abundance allowed better stratification of treatment outcomes in patients with NSCLC rather than simply assessing its presence or absence. Patients harboring normal (positive relative abundance <4.799%) levels of *A. muciniphila* at baseline had a richer GM composition and experienced greater clinical benefit from ICB (62). Conversely, patients with abnormal (relative abundance >4.799%) levels of *A. muciniphila*, or lack of the bacterium, had significantly reduced overall survival and a tolerogenic microbiota dominated by the *Enterocloster* genus. *A. muciniphila* SGB9226 can be used as a proxy for gut dysbiosis, but it also has therapeutic potential as a probiotic. Hence, a qPCR-based diagnosis identifying patients devoid of SGB9226 is being used to select patients for a phase 1 trial aimed at compensating them with an immunogenic strain of *Akkermansia* (the live bacterial product Oncobax®AK) in patients with RCC and NSCLC receiving first-line ICB therapy (NCT05865730).

The health-related *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* is another bacteria species associated with ICB benefit (55, 63, 64) as patients with localized melanoma who harbored higher levels of *F.*

prausnitzii had greater disease-free survival (65). Iadsee et al. showed that the opportunistic pathogen *Erysipelatoclostridium ramosum* is also enriched in gut mucosal and fecal samples of colorectal cancer (CRC) patients (16S rRNA-seq and qPCR), allowing them to discriminate between healthy volunteers and patients with adenoma (66). Remarkably, the qPCR assay they developed showed a specificity of 72.7% and a sensitivity of 64.7%, leading them to propose *E. ramosum*-qPCR as a candidate noninvasive biomarker for CRC diagnosis (66). If the presence of *E. ramosum* in the ileum can be associated with the efficacy of ICB and chemotherapy in CRC, independent of microsatellite stability status, it could open new opportunities to apply *E. ramosum*-qPCR in the immuno-oncology setting (67).

3.2 Fecal scores for gut dysbiosis

Gut dysbiosis is a deviated repertoire of the GM composition compared with the healthy status, but there is currently no consensus about what this actually means. Furthermore, there appears to be no discernible pattern at the phylogenetic level regarding which bacterial species are beneficial for ICB efficacy (68). This implies that a dichotomous classification of “good” versus “bad” bacteria at the species level may be inadequate, and a more holistic approach is required.

Based on fecal MGS data from a retrospective discovery cohort of 245 patients with advanced NSCLC treated with ICB, Derosa et al. constructed networks of co-abundant taxa that clustered into species-interacting groups (SIGs) and correlated these SIGs with overall survival at 12 months (69). Thirty-seven and 45 species identified with MGS could be grouped into clusters associated with ICB resistance (SIG1) and ICB response (SIG2), respectively. From a whole-population-based network down to a unidimensional score at an individual level, Derosa et al. calculated the SIG1/SIG2 ratio, which considered the number of microbial species in each SIG present in the baseline stool sample for each patient. When this ratio was poorly discriminant (“grey zone”), *A. muciniphila* trichotomic stratification (62) was considered to obtain the final “TOPOSCORE” (69). NSCLC patients who were SIG2+ experienced improved overall survival in the discovery (N = 245) and validation cohorts (N = 254) and in a third cohort of urinary tract cancer patients amenable to ICB (N = 216). Finally, the 83 MGS-based TOPOSCORE could be translated into a 21-bacterial probe set to standardize qPCR-based scoring. It could also be used as a diagnostic tool for gut dysbiosis to select patients for MCIs.

Other methods using similar approaches have been proposed. For example, Gupta et al. described a predictive Gut Microbiome Health Index (GMHI), a biologically interpretable mathematical formula using 50 MGS species. The GMHI could stratify groups into health and disease status with an accuracy of 73.7% (70). Gacesa et al. were able to find significant differences between individuals with self-reported diseases using the GMHI (20). In a Vietnamese study of breast cancer patients, most of the study’s participants had a negative GMHI at baseline, indicating an unhealthy microbiota composition (71). The authors attributed the increased reduction of GMHI observed after breast surgery to perioperative antibiotics prophylaxis (71).

To date, GMHI has not been tested in the immuno-oncology setting, and qPCR-based TOPOSCORE requires prospective validation. Regardless, such holistic approaches open up new opportunities for developing microbiota-based predictive scores to better guide precision medicine, clinical management and compensatory measures in interceptive and therapeutic immuno-oncology practices (72).

4. Gut barrier-related markers

The gut barrier has physical and chemical properties. The physical barrier relies on a single layer of enterocytes joined together by proteins that form tight junctions and prevent leakage from the gut lumen. The chemical barrier relies on compounds secreted by immune and non-immune cells within the lamina propria, such as secretory immunoglobulin A (sIgA) produced by plasma cells or antimicrobial peptides like REG3 γ by ileal cells. The luminal side of the enterocytes is overlaid by a mucus layer, which acts as both a physical and chemical barrier. It provides lubrication and acts as

a moist habitat for GM. Any disruption of the mucus layer exposes enterocytes to the content of the lumen, increasing the risk of damage and subsequent translocation of microbes systemically.

The polarization of the intestinal epithelial cells – where one side faces the gut lumen and the other faces the body tissue – is one mechanism by which the epithelial barrier integrity is maintained. Loss of polarity increases with age and is found to be related to deviations in GM composition and local inflammation (73). The stress polarity signalling (SPS) pathway has been described in which the metabolic sensor, adenosine monophosphate-activated protein kinase (AMPK), acts via its effector, GIV (G-alpha interacting vesicle-associated protein or Girdin) (73). This SPS pathway makes it possible to increase epithelial polarity exclusively during energetic stress and, importantly, helps suppress tumor formation in the colon (73). Metabolic pathways can reinforce the SPS pathway. It is well established that metformin treatment, widely prescribed for type 2 diabetes, works in an AMPK-dependent manner on gut and blood barriers and epithelial tight junctions (74–76).

Yonekura et al. have shown that extraintestinal carcinogenesis can cause a “stress ileopathy”, which is characterized by an ectopic accumulation of enteroendocrine cells and an imbalance between sympathetic and cholinergic signalling, leading to a protracted intestinal dysbiosis (44). The carcinogenesis induced a release of antimicrobial peptides such as REG3 γ by ileal cells and a transient epithelial barrier permeability, commonly known as “leaky gut syndrome” (44). Additionally, the Corticotropin-Releasing Factor receptor 2 (CRF2) and its ligands Urocortin2 and 3 (Ucn2/3) have been defined as a stress neuromediator system that can negatively affect the intestinal barrier and induce inflammation (77). This mechanism is supported by the loss of cellular organization mediated by the CRF2 signaling and has been incriminated in colorectal tumor progression (77).

4.1 Gut inflammation biomarkers

Several biomarkers are used to discern gut barrier dysfunctions and alterations. Circulating biomarkers that can reflect gut barrier functions include citrulline, intestinal fatty acid-binding protein (iFABPs), soluble CD14 (sCD14), soluble ST2 (sST2 / sIL33R), and zonulin as a proxy for tight junctions and intestinal permeability. These biomarkers can help identify enterocyte damage and dysfunction in intensive care patients (78). The tight junction-related proteins are claudins, occludin, junctional adhesion molecules, and scaffold protein zonula occludens. Osteopontin (OPN), also called Secreted phosphoprotein 1 (SPP1), has been described as a regulator of the tight junctions complex, preventing dephosphorylation and internalization of the occludin (79). Intestinal hyperpermeability can be caused by multiple factors, such as the type of diet, comedications (e.g., antibiotics), and comorbidities (e.g., inflammatory diseases). For example, a higher consumption of the typical Western diet is associated with increased gut permeability, as assessed by levels of sCD14 found in circulation (80). Levels of serum and fecal calprotectins (S100A08/09/11/12) and fecal lactoferrin or Lipocalin-2 (LCN2) are efficient biomarkers used for evaluating gut barrier fitness in inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) (81). Additionally, circulating levels of serum lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-binding protein (LBP), TNF α , IL-6, calprotectins, and C-reactive protein are surrogates of intestinal inflammation and are commonly found associated with CRC (82). Notably, bacteria such as *A. muciniphila*, which we previously described as a well-known bacterium associated with an antiageing and healthy status and improved ICB efficacy (38, 83), can reduce these inflammatory markers (84). High levels of anti-flagellin IgA and LBP are associated with an increased risk of hepatitis B virus-related hepatocellular carcinoma (85). Fecal calprotectin levels have been found to be positively correlated with tolerogenic oral taxa such as *Veillonella* spp. and *Fusobacterium* spp. (86). Integrative scores for gut health that are based on a combination of fecal MGS signatures and gut inflammation biomarkers are interesting approaches that could be further explored for clinical applications (86).

Other studies explored imaging technologies (i.e. FDG-PET/CT) to quantify gut inflammation, especially in the context of IBDs (81). However, this has shown inconsistent results. For example, Sachpekidis and colleagues used [18F]FDG PET/CT to demonstrate that the physiologic colonic radiotracer uptake (SUV) before ICB therapy could not independently predict patient survival in advanced melanoma patients (87). In contrast, the volumetric PET parameter

colonic total lesion glycolysis did show a significant correlation with progression-free survival (87).

4.2 Gut-vascular barrier-related biomarkers

While the epithelial barrier acts as an indiscriminate physical barrier, nutrients from food still need to enter general circulation. The gut-vascular barrier – comprised of endothelial cells (EC), pericytes, and glial cells – is more selective and regulates the passage of small molecules into the bloodstream. However, the permeability of the gut-vascular barrier can be modulated by metabolites such as bile acids via their receptors [e.g., farnesoid X receptor (FXR)]. For example, bacterial translocation was modulated by bile acids in parallel with an increase in the glycoprotein plasmalemma vesicle-associated protein-1 (PV-1) expression on blood vessels in an experimental cirrhosis model. In contrast, FXR-agonists reduced the incidence of bacterial translocation (88). PV-1 expression can also be used to evaluate abnormal gut-vascular barrier permeability as its loss compromises endothelial barrier functions (89). Conversely, its increase on colonic CD31⁺ EC has also been associated with bacterial translocation to the liver and the formation of pre-metastatic niches (90). PV-1 has also been described as an independent marker of CRC recurrence (90), thus making it of great interest in MCI studies.

EC express adhesion molecules (i.e., VCAM-1 and ICAM-1), which are modulated by inflammation. MAdCAM-1 is also highly expressed by EC in the lamina propria and mLN. Correlating with ileal MAdCAM-1 expression, soluble MAdCAM-1 (sMAdCAM-1) levels determined by an ELISA have been associated with prognosis in four independent cohorts of ICB-treated patients with NSCLC (discovery and validation), RCC, and bladder cancer (43). Overall, a lower level of sMAdCAM-1 at the beginning of treatment was associated with antibiotics intake, antibiotics-independent gut dysbiosis, and worse treatment outcomes in patients treated with ICB. Furthermore, a Cox regression analysis showed that sMAdCAM-1 is an independent prognostic factor in both cohorts of patients with NSCLC and RCC (43, 91). Interestingly, higher levels of sMAdCAM-1 were also associated with richer GM and reduced abundance of species from the *Enterocloster* genus. These results suggest that sMAdCAM-1 might be a good proxy for gut dysbiosis and help guide the selection of patients who would be more amenable to MCI.

EC and GM also play a role in promoting metastasis. GM produces molecules leading to the production of pro-angiogenic factors (VEGF, IL8/CXCL8, COX2), and, consequently to increased angiogenesis which is involved in tumor growth and metastasis (92). In ICB-treated melanoma patients, genes encoding proinflammatory cytokines (i.e., IL-1 β and CXCL8), diverse transcription factors, and superoxide dismutase were differentially expressed between responders and non-responders. This was associated with an over-representation of Gram-negative bacteria in feces, suggesting that LPS could trigger inflammatory processes (56). In the first clinical trial using FMT to revert primary resistance to ICB in melanoma patients, plasma IL8/CXCL8 was found to be a marker of unresponsiveness (9).

5. Lymphocyte responses to commensals

Accumulating evidence over the past decade demonstrates that tumors are not sterile, and each malignancy contains unique microbiomes of uncertain origin (93–97). The first successful demonstration of this point was published by Nejman et al. (98), who found that each cancer type has a unique microbiome by analyzing 1,526 archived tumor samples and adjacent healthy tissues from breast, lung, ovary, pancreas, melanoma, bone, and brain tumors. How these microbiomes establish themselves and where they originate is still under investigation (95). Regardless of their origins, the impact of tumor microbiomes on the intratumoral lymphocyte response to cancer could be critical for immunotherapy outcomes.

For example, Toll-like receptor (TLR) agonists improve ICB therapies (99, 100). Microbes contain a variety of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) that activate TLRs, which promote a more robust immune reaction, and, consequently, a better anti-cancer immune response.

Immune-related adverse events frequently follow ICB therapy and are most common in the mucosal sites (101), especially the gut (102). Furthermore, researchers have observed that immunotherapy patients who develop colitis tend to respond better to the treatment compared with patients who do not develop gut-related pathologies (103, 104). ICB-induced gut inflammation could create an environment where gut bacteria escape the gut lumen, supplement existing tumor microbiomes, and support lymphocyte activation and positive treatment outcomes through an *in situ* adjuvant effect (68). Choi et al. (46) supported this theory by using an *in vivo* mouse melanoma model to demonstrate that DCs transport gut bacteria to secondary lymphoid organs following ICB treatment. These bacteria then systematically disseminated through the animals via the vasculature and colonized distal solid tumors and influenced T cell activation, thus improving ICB therapeutic outcomes in these models. This mechanism has not been validated in the clinic. Still, low-level bacteraemia in patients with ICB-induced colitis could indicate that they will experience a superior benefit from ICB therapies.

Another popular hypothesis in the literature posits that gut commensals act as a reservoir of peptides closely resembling tumor-associated antigens (TAAs) (105–107). Computational modeling has demonstrated a significant similarity between TAAs and epitopes derived from GM, which could facilitate cross-reactivity vis-a-vis of microbial and tumour-derived antigens in memory CD8⁺ T cells (106), a phenomenon known as 'antigen mimicry'. Our laboratory recently demonstrated antigen mimicry between TAAs and microbial-derived peptides *in vivo* using mouse tumor models; we identified an epitope in the tape measure protein (TMP) of an enterococcal bacteriophage found in *Enterococcus hirae* that can trigger a memory T cell response against a TAA oncogene (108). Notably, C57BL/6 mice colonized with *E. hirae* showed improved responses to ICB against the MCA-205 sarcoma and TC1 lung cancer models (but not the MC38 colorectal model). Further analysis revealed homology between the bacteria-derived TMP epitope and an epitope from the tumor-derived proteasome 20S subunit beta 4 (PSMB4) protein, thus suggesting that CD8⁺ T cells activated by *E. hirae* were cross-reactive to tumors expressing PSMB4. We retrospectively analyzed data from 76 NSCLC and RCC patients to put this finding in a clinical context and found that patients with *Enterococcus faecalis* colonies harboring the TMP peptide also tended to have an improved response to ICB.

Antigen mimicry between microbial peptides and TAAs was also recently demonstrated in glioblastoma patients when tumor-infiltrating and circulating T cell clones were found to recognize both microbial and glioblastoma antigens (105). Furthermore, these T cells were not reactive exclusively to a single bacterial peptide but could recognise multiple microbiota-derived peptides from several sources. For example, one T cell clone isolated from a tumor responded to peptides from *Bacteroides fragilis*, *Ruminococcus bromii*, *Alistipes* spp., and *Eubacterium* spp. While this study did not investigate the impact of these clones on treatment outcomes, it does suggest that a diverse set of gut commensals could provide peptides with homology shared with TAA.

Antigen mimicry implies that two epitopes of high homology can induce an equivalent immune response. However, there also exists the possibility that intratumoral bacteria may provide the existing antigenic pool within the tumor microenvironment (TME). For example, cytotoxic CD8⁺ T cell activity against cancer can also be promoted by HLA-restricted peptides from intracellular bacteria found in melanoma cells (109). The clinical implications of these findings still need to be investigated. However, any potential clinical application as an MCI must assume that cancerous cells retain functional peptide-loading machinery for HLA molecules.

Tumor-infiltrating bacteria may also influence anti-tumour B cells through T cell-dependent activation. CD4⁺ follicular helper T cell (T_{fh} cell) and CD8⁺ T cell collaboration can be enhanced by B cell recognition of TAAs, thus bolstering anti-tumour immunity in lung adenocarcinoma and subsequently improving the efficacy of PD-1 blockade therapy in some patients (110). Therefore, B cells activated by T_{fh} cells with a microbial peptide cross-reactive to a TAA would increase the secretion of anti-tumour antibodies and facilitate an anti-tumour humoral reaction. Indeed, increased serum concentrations of CXCL13 – a B lymphocyte chemoattractant – have been positively correlated with ICB treatment outcomes in both lung cancer (111) and bladder cancer (112). Patients with

favorable treatment outcomes also showed increased serum levels of cross-reactive antibodies between microbes and tumors. Ng et al. (111) demonstrated that endogenous retrovirus (ERV) – targeting antibodies improved ICB treatments in mice and suggested it could be a possible biomarker for ICB treatment in NSCLC patients.

Similarly, Goubet et al. (112) demonstrated that patients with muscle-invasive bladder cancer (MIBC) exhibiting elevated serum levels of IgG antibodies against uropathogenic *E. coli* (but no other urinary commensals) experienced enhanced responses to anti-PD1 therapy. Their study further revealed a significant correlation between baseline circulating Tfh cells, the presence of tertiary lymphoid structures (TLS), and B cell activation with the efficacy of ICB treatment. Uropathogenic *E. coli* was also found within tumors and myeloid cells, further demonstrating that tumors are not sterile tissues. This study highlighted that treating freshly dissociated MIBC tissues with exogenous *E. coli* post-cystectomy led to the activation of antibody-secreting cells and intratumoral Tfh cells in treatment-responsive patients. This process also resulted in the secretion of CXCL13 and CCL19, chemokines characteristic of TLS formation (113, 114), though it was notable that no increased IFN γ release was observed. The clinical implications of these findings are still under investigation, but they suggest a novel mechanism through which intratumoral bacteria can modulate lymphocyte responses and influence therapy outcomes.

Cancer-associated microbial neoantigens are promising targets for therapeutic or preventive strategies. Indeed, Chen et al. (115) demonstrated this treatment strategy using a mouse B16.F0 OVA melanoma model. Topical application of a transgenic *Staphylococcus epidermidis* modified to express the OVA peptide was sufficient to improve tumor control and ICB therapeutic efficacy. Developing such a strategy as an MCI would significantly enhance the treatment efficacy of current ICB therapies, making it a critical intervention for improving patient outcomes. Additionally, Wang and colleagues showed that the protumoral anaerobic *Fusobacterium nucleatum* induced an immunosuppressive TME in CRC models (116). Furthermore, patients with localized CRC who received anaerobe-targeting antibiotics (nitroimidazole or lincomycin classes) before surgery had significantly longer disease-free survival when compared with patients who either did not receive antibiotics treatment or received different classes of antibiotics. Additionally, antibiotic-loaded liposomes designed to target CRC promoted the release of cancer-specific microbial neoantigens, which elicited microbial-specific T-cell immunity (116). CRC patients will be randomized to metronidazole or placebo in a phase 2 clinical trial (NCT04264676) based on the *F. nucleatum* - deltaCT value (qPCR) in colon tissue samples before receiving chemotherapy.

Currently, laboratory and diagnostic techniques that enable the characterisation of potential intratumoral bacteria rely on molecular methods (i.e., WGS and 16S rRNA-seq), culturomics, and histological examination of tissue sections (95). However, no standardized methods exist to assess intratumoural microbiomes and their impact on lymphocyte responses. This is a critical unmet need that could better inform caregivers and researchers about what impact tumor microbiomes may have on ICB therapy outcomes.

6. Microbial-derived metabolites

The human GM produces various molecules that can impact intestinal fitness and health. Advances in liquid and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry techniques (LC-MS and GC-MS, respectively) have enabled the mapping of clinically relevant microbial-related metabolites in immuno-oncology. Microbial metabolic pathways can also be evaluated in fecal MGS using bioinformatics genome databases (117). Bacterial metabolites have gained additional attention because of their potential to impact cancer immunosurveillance by modulating innate and cognate immune responses (42, 55).

Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) such as acetate, propionate, butyrate, pentanoate (or valerate), and malonate are key players in host physiology and the interplay between diet and GM and host metabolism and immunity (42, 55). SCFAs are immunostimulatory metabolites (IMMs). When they interact with G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) – especially GPR41, GPR43, and GPR109A –

they initiate signalling cascades that regulate the activity of histone deacetylase (HDAC) inhibitors and influence gene expression (118). This can increase CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ effector T cell activity and may regulate suppressor Tregs functions (118, 119). For example, Luu et al. showed that two strains of *Megasphaera massiliensis* (DSM 26228 and NCIMB 42787) were capable of producing higher titers of the SCFAs pentanoate and butyrate compared to 14 bacterial species from the most common phyla in the human gut (119). Pentanoate and butyrate increased the efficacy of human and murine CAR-T cells (119) and may circumvent the altered composition of fecal metabolites after allogeneic transplantation therapies (120, 121).

The enterohepatic recirculation of bile acids exerts important regulatory effects on host functions, and abnormalities in bile acids metabolism are implicated in cancer immunosurveillance. Intestinal bacteria metabolize the bile acids produced and secreted by the gallbladder and the liver. The enterohepatic cycle of the bile acids consists of the production of secondary bile acids by intestinal bacteria and their absorption and recirculation to the liver through the enterohepatic circulation. Thus, gut dysbiosis can perturb fecal and plasmatic bile acids composition, and lead to a downregulation of MAdCAM-1, and the exodus of immunosuppressive enterotropic T cells towards tumor beds (43, 122). Indeed, secondary bile acids such as the lithocholic acid (LCA) or the deoxycholic acid, formed by intestinal bacteria were responsible for MAdCAM-1 downregulation on endothelial cells (43). In addition to conventional biosynthetic pathways involved in bile acids metabolism by the microbiota, new pathways have been discovered in centenarians known to have a unique GM composition (27, 28, 123). In these centenarians, *Odoribacteraceae* strains have been identified as potent producers of isoforms of LCA (27). Primary bile acids (such as cholic acid, chenodeoxycholic acid and tauro β -muricholic acid) are predominantly IMM (65, 124). A higher abundance of cholic acid was associated with improved recurrence-free survival after surgery in localized melanoma patients (65). Bile acids receptors such as FXR, or Takeda-G-protein-receptor-5 (TRG5) are expressed by immune and tumoral cells, and can impact anti-tumoral mechanisms. Indeed, the microbial transformation of bile acids impacts T cell-driven immune responses through FXR activation (43, 121, 124), and FXR overexpression by cancer cells is associated with cancer progression (125), and PD-L1 upregulation in the TME (126). Thus, FXR antagonists (i.e. Z-guggulsterone) are promising strategies in immuno-oncology (43, 126).

The microbial-derived metabolite desaminotyrosine (DAT), a product of tyrosine metabolism, induces an epithelial barrier protective effect through type I interferon (IFN-I) signaling (127–129). DAT improves ICB efficacy, modifies the TME with increased activated T and natural killer (NK) cells and compensates for the negative effects of antibiotics (128). Interestingly, by compounding fecal levels of DAT together with SCFAs butyrate and propionate, branched-chain fatty acid isovaleric acid, and ICA, Orberg et al. established the IMM-risk that is associated with clinical outcomes after allogeneic hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (120).

Aside from body fluids, GM-related biomarkers can be studied in other biological matrices, such as breath. A correlation between volatile organic compounds (VOCs) measured by GC–MS technique in exhaled breath and the fecal microbiota composition has been described in gastric cancer patients (130). These VOCs comprise gut-related metabolites such as hydrocarbons, alcohols, aromatics, ketones, ethers, and organosulfides (130).

7. Future directions

This review has identified and discussed several gut-related biomarkers identified in the literature, methods that can take advantage of host-microbiota parameters, and their biological consequences on anticancer immunity. However, these biomarkers still require analytical and clinical validation before being implemented in routine clinical care (131). Further development is also required, as there is currently a lack of technical standardization and definitions for clinically relevant and informative values. Publicly available standard protocols should be referenced to optimize comparability between GM studies (61, 132, 133), but more clinical investigations are required to address these issues. Indeed, out of 133 clinical trials evaluating different MCIs (26 not yet recruiting

and 107 recruiting), only three use gut-microbiota-related biomarkers or previous use of antibiotics to guide the inclusion of recipients (NCT05865730, NCT06218602, NCT04264676).

Moreover, we should move towards more equitable GM research through international collaborations (134, 135). Earlier, we highlighted how the composition of the GM is intimately linked with human culture through diet and lifestyle. Thus, it stands to reason that sufficient representation of different racial and ethnic populations in future GM studies would support the development of more robust and reliable biomarkers.

Methods to study the GM continue to evolve and are becoming increasingly more accessible and less expensive. Untargeted metagenomics analyses like MGS remain the gold standard for enabling not only taxonomic but also functional (e.g., metabolic pathways) profiling – especially in discovery settings. Untargeted metabolomics similarly provides a global and comprehensive analysis. Conversely, targeted metagenomics (e.g., 16S rRNA-seq) and metabolomics have the advantage of lower costs and can be useful in validation settings. The research question and study design will guide the method of choice.

Gut-related biomarkers are diagnostic biomarkers that can indicate a positive diagnosis of gut dysbiosis at the start of ICB (Figure 1B), thus helping to identify patients who require complementary treatment with MCIs (Figure 2A) (136). Increasing evidence demonstrates that the GM can also be manipulated to produce optimal clinical outcomes. Further investigations are needed to determine dosing, scheduling, and routes of administration for MCIs meant to improve or supplement current immunotherapy strategies. The management of MCIs' therapies (including FMT) and the impact they may have on therapies like ICB will present new challenges for the clinical care team. This includes creating an efficient and cost-effective workflow that moves between patient identification, disease classification, personalized MCIs administration, and toxicity management. This must also be accomplished while integrating clinical and biological information from various “-omics” and molecular biology platforms through artificial intelligence. When properly validated, the biomarkers we described in this review can be useful tools to follow the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of MCIs (Figure 2B).

The interactions between the host and their microbiota are fascinating, complex, and multifaceted, with evidence repeatedly demonstrating the critical impact it has on cancer progression and therapeutic outcome. While this review has focused exclusively on how GM interactions could be leveraged to improve clinical outcomes, the impact of extraintestinal microbial communities (e.g., skin and oral microbiota) on cancer therapies should also be explored. By leveraging these interactions, we will continue to uncover exciting opportunities for identifying useful biomarkers and developing novel preventive and therapeutic strategies across various cancer types for all ages (55).

Table 1 *Specific gut metagenomics species are associated with ICB outcomes in patients with cancer.*

Country, reference	Cancer	Stage	N	Therapy	Definition of R	Alpha-diversity	Species
USA (63)	Melanoma	Advanced	39	PD-1 ± CTLA-4	SD + CR + PR	R = NR	R: <i>F. prausnitzii</i> , <i>D. formicigenerans</i> , <i>B. caccae</i> , <i>S. parasanguinis</i> , <i>H. filiformis</i> , <i>B. thetaiotaomicron</i>
USA (56)	Melanoma	IV	94	PD-1	SD + CR + PR	R = NR	R: <i>E. rectale</i> , <i>Blautia</i> spp, <i>R. torques</i> , <i>R. gnavus</i> , <i>A. hadrus</i> , <i>Bifidobacterium</i>
UK, Spain, NLD (137)	Melanoma	IV	175	PD-1 + CTLA-4	SD + CR + PR	R = NR	R: <i>A. muciniphila</i> , <i>Roseburia</i> , <i>L. vaginalis</i>
Croatia (138)	Melanoma	IV	15	PD-1 ± CTLA-4	CR > 12 months. Early if CR achieved < 9 months.	Early R = late R	Early R: <i>Barnesiella intestinihominis</i> , <i>Sutterella wadsworthensis</i> , <i>Bacteroides finegoldii</i> Late R: <i>Coprococcus comes</i> , <i>Bifidobacterium pseudocatenulatum</i>
France (38)	NSCLC and RCC	IV	153	PD-1	CR + PR or SD + CR + PR > 3 months	R > NR	R: <i>A. muciniphila</i> , <i>Eubacterium</i> , <i>Alistipes</i> spp, <i>Ruminococcaceae</i> , <i>Lachnospiraceae</i> , <i>Firmicutes</i>
Hungary (139)	NSCLC	IIIB and IV	62 + 60 V	PD-1	SD + CR + PR > 6 months	R = NR	R: <i>A. shahii</i> , <i>B. viscerioli</i> , <i>B. faecalis</i> , <i>Bacteroides</i> sp. <i>A1C1</i> and <i>A. finegoldii</i> NR: <i>S. salivarius</i> , <i>S. vestibularis</i> , <i>S. parasanguinis</i> , <i>B. longum</i> , <i>B. adolescentis</i> and <i>B. breve</i>
USA (140)	NSCLC	IV	13	PD-1 + chemotherapy	CR + PR > 3-6 months	R = NR	R: <i>Firmicutes</i> NR: <i>Bacteroidetes</i>
France (31)	RCC	IV	69	PD-1	SD + CR + PR > 12 months	R > NR	R: <i>A. muciniphila</i> , <i>Eubacterium</i> sp, <i>B. salyersiae</i> NR: <i>H. hathewayi</i> , <i>E. clostridioformis</i>
China (141)	NPC	Recurrent or IV	50	PD-1	PR	R = NR	R: <i>Clostridiales</i> order NR: <i>R. bacterium</i> , <i>Ruminococcus</i> sp., <i>Ruminiclostridium</i> genus
Canada (142)	Pan-cancer	IV	62	PD-(L)1 ± CTLA-4	ARe versus PRe	ARe=PRe	No significant different taxa between ARe and PRe.

Acquired resistance (ARe); Complete response (CR); Immune-checkpoint blockade (ICB); Major pathologic response (MPR); Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC); Netherlands (NLD); Non-responder patient (NR); Number of patients (N); Partial response (PR); Primary resistance (PRe); Renal cell carcinoma (RCC); Responder patients (R); Stable disease (SD); United Kingdom (UK); Validation (V).

References

1. Bray F, Laversanne M, Weiderpass E, Soerjomataram I. 2021. The ever-increasing importance of cancer as a leading cause of premature death worldwide. *Cancer*. 127(16):3029–30
2. Zhao J, Xu L, Sun J, Song M, Wang L, et al. 2023. Global trends in incidence, death, burden and risk factors of early-onset cancer from 1990 to 2019. *bmjonc*. 2(1):e000049
3. Wu Q, Qian W, Sun X, Jiang S. 2022. Small-molecule inhibitors, immune checkpoint inhibitors, and more: FDA-approved novel therapeutic drugs for solid tumors from 1991 to 2021. *J Hematol Oncol*. 15(1):143
4. Chen DS, Mellman I. 2017. Elements of cancer immunity and the cancer–immune set point. *Nature*. 541(7637):321–30
5. De Visser KE, Joyce JA. 2023. The evolving tumor microenvironment: From cancer initiation to metastatic outgrowth. *Cancer Cell*. 41(3):374–403
6. Hanahan D. 2022. Hallmarks of Cancer: New Dimensions. *Cancer Discovery*. 12(1):31–46
7. Derosa L, Routy B, Desilets A, Daillère R, Terrisse S, et al. 2021. Microbiota-Centered Interventions: The Next Breakthrough in Immuno-Oncology? *Cancer Discovery*. 11(10):2396–2412
8. Baruch EN, Youngster I, Ben-Betzalel G, Ortenberg R, Lahat A, et al. 2021. Fecal microbiota transplant promotes response in immunotherapy-refractory melanoma patients. *Science*. 371(6529):602–9
9. Davar D, Dzutsev AK, McCulloch JA, Rodrigues RR, Chauvin J-M, et al. 2021. Fecal microbiota transplant overcomes resistance to anti–PD-1 therapy in melanoma patients. *Science*. 371(6529):595–602
10. Routy B, Lenehan JG, Miller WH, Jamal R, Messaoudene M, et al. 2023. Fecal microbiota transplantation plus anti-PD-1 immunotherapy in advanced melanoma: a phase I trial. *Nat Med*
11. Dizman N, Meza L, Bergerot P, Alcantara M, Dorff T, et al. 2022. Nivolumab plus ipilimumab with or without live bacterial supplementation in metastatic renal cell carcinoma: a randomized

phase 1 trial. *Nat Med.* 28(4):704–12

12. Ebrahimi H, Meza LA, Lee K, Malhotra J, Alcantara M, et al. 2023. Effect of CBM588 in combination with cabozantinib plus nivolumab for patients (pts) with metastatic renal cell carcinoma (mRCC): A randomized clinical trial. *JCO.* 41(17_suppl):LBA104–LBA104
13. Donaldson GP, Lee SM, Mazmanian SK. 2016. Gut biogeography of the bacterial microbiota. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 14(1):20–32
14. Sender R, Fuchs S, Milo R. 2016. Revised Estimates for the Number of Human and Bacteria Cells in the Body. *PLoS Biol.* 14(8):e1002533
15. Forster SC, Kumar N, Anonye BO, Almeida A, Viciani E, et al. 2019. A human gut bacterial genome and culture collection for improved metagenomic analyses. *Nat Biotechnol.* 37(2):186–92
16. Dethlefsen L, McFall-Ngai M, Relman DA. 2007. An ecological and evolutionary perspective on human-microbe mutualism and disease. *Nature.* 449(7164):811–18
17. Senghor B, Sokhna C, Ruimy R, Lagier J-C. 2018. Gut microbiota diversity according to dietary habits and geographical provenance. *Human Microbiome Journal.* 7–8:1–9
18. Kamada N, Seo S-U, Chen GY, Núñez G. 2013. Role of the gut microbiota in immunity and inflammatory disease. *Nat Rev Immunol.* 13(5):321–35
19. Wu H-J, Wu E. 2012. The role of gut microbiota in immune homeostasis and autoimmunity. *Gut Microbes.* 3(1):4–14
20. Gacesa R, Kurilshikov A, Vich Vila A, Sinha T, Klaassen MAY, et al. 2022. Environmental factors shaping the gut microbiome in a Dutch population. *Nature.* 604(7907):732–39
21. Rothschild D, Weissbrod O, Barkan E, Kurilshikov A, Korem T, et al. 2018. Environment dominates over host genetics in shaping human gut microbiota. *Nature.* 555(7695):210–15
22. Song SJ, Lauber C, Costello EK, Lozupone CA, Humphrey G, et al. 2013. Cohabiting family members share microbiota with one another and with their dogs. *eLife.* 2:e00458
23. Xie H, Guo R, Zhong H, Feng Q, Lan Z, et al. 2016. Shotgun Metagenomics of 250 Adult

Twins Reveals Genetic and Environmental Impacts on the Gut Microbiome. *Cell Systems*. 3(6):572-584.e3

24. Rampelli S, Soverini M, D'Amico F, Barone M, Tavella T, et al. 2020. Shotgun Metagenomics of Gut Microbiota in Humans with up to Extreme Longevity and the Increasing Role of Xenobiotic Degradation. *mSystems*. 5(2):e00124-20
25. Ghosh TS, Das M, Jeffery IB, O'Toole PW. 2020. Adjusting for age improves identification of gut microbiome alterations in multiple diseases. *Elife*. 9:e50240
26. Luan Z, Sun G, Huang Y, Yang Y, Yang R, et al. 2020. Metagenomics Study Reveals Changes in Gut Microbiota in Centenarians: A Cohort Study of Hainan Centenarians. *Front Microbiol*. 11:1474
27. Sato Y, Atarashi K, Plichta DR, Arai Y, Sasajima S, et al. 2021. Novel bile acid biosynthetic pathways are enriched in the microbiome of centenarians. *Nature*. 599(7885):458–64
28. Wang J, Qie J, Zhu D, Zhang X, Zhang Q, et al. 2022. The landscape in the gut microbiome of long-lived families reveals new insights on longevity and aging - relevant neural and immune function. *Gut Microbes*. 14(1):2107288
29. Wu H, Esteve E, Tremaroli V, Khan MT, Caesar R, et al. 2017. Metformin alters the gut microbiome of individuals with treatment-naive type 2 diabetes, contributing to the therapeutic effects of the drug. *Nat Med*. 23(7):850–58
30. Floris Imhann, Marc Jan Bonder, Arnau Vich Vila, Jingyuan Fu, Zlatan Mujagic, et al. 2016. Proton pump inhibitors affect the gut microbiome. *Gut*. 65(5):740
31. Derosa L, Routy B, Fidelle M, Iebba V, Alla L, et al. 2020. Gut Bacteria Composition Drives Primary Resistance to Cancer Immunotherapy in Renal Cell Carcinoma Patients. *European Urology*
32. Derosa L, Hellmann MD, Spaziano M, Halpenny D, Fidelle M, et al. 2018. Negative association of antibiotics on clinical activity of immune checkpoint inhibitors in patients with advanced renal cell and non-small-cell lung cancer. *Annals of Oncology*. 29(6):1437–44

33. Derosa L, Zitvogel L. 2020. Antibiotics impair immunotherapy for urothelial cancer. *Nature Reviews Urology*
34. Elkrif A, Derosa L, Kroemer G, Zitvogel L, Routy B. 2019. The negative impact of antibiotics on outcomes in cancer patients treated with immunotherapy: a new independent prognostic factor? *Annals of Oncology*. 30(10):1572–79
35. Yang Z, Wei S, Liu L. 2020. Antibiotic Treatment and Immune Checkpoint Inhibitor Therapy in Patients With Cancer. *JAMA Oncology*. 6(4):587
36. Serpas V, Rogers JE, Xiao L, Mola-Rudd K, Dasari A, et al. 2020. Impact of antibiotic exposure on the efficacy of immune checkpoint blockade in MSI-H metastatic CRC. *JCO*. 38(4_suppl):161–161
37. Pinato DJ, Howlett S, Ottaviani D, Urus H, Patel A, et al. 2019. Association of Prior Antibiotic Treatment With Survival and Response to Immune Checkpoint Inhibitor Therapy in Patients With Cancer. *JAMA Oncology*. 5(12):1774
38. Routy B, Le Chatelier E, Derosa L, Duong CPM, Alou MT, et al. 2018. Gut microbiome influences efficacy of PD-1–based immunotherapy against epithelial tumors. *Science*. 359(6371):91–97
39. Peled JU, Gomes ALC, Devlin SM, Littmann ER, Taur Y, et al. 2020. Microbiota as Predictor of Mortality in Allogeneic Hematopoietic-Cell Transplantation. *N Engl J Med*. 382(9):822–34
40. Stein-Thoeringer CK, Saini NY, Zamir E, Blumenberg V, Schubert M-L, et al. 2023. A non-antibiotic-disrupted gut microbiome is associated with clinical responses to CD19-CAR-T cell cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Med*. 29(4):906–16
41. Smith M, Dai A, Ghilardi G, Amelsberg KV, Devlin SM, et al. 2022. Gut microbiome correlates of response and toxicity following anti-CD19 CAR T cell therapy. *Nat Med*. 28(4):713–23
42. Zhang Z, Tang H, Chen P, Xie H, Tao Y. 2019. Demystifying the manipulation of host immunity, metabolism, and extraintestinal tumors by the gut microbiome. *Sig Transduct*

Target Ther. 4(1):41

43. Fidelle M, Rauber C, Alves Costa Silva C, Tian A-L, Lahmar I, et al. 2023. A microbiota-modulated checkpoint directs immunosuppressive intestinal T cells into cancers. *Science*. 380(6649):eabo2296
44. Yonekura S, Terrisse S, Alves Costa Silva C, Lafarge A, Iebba V, et al. 2022. Cancer Induces a Stress Ileopathy Depending on β -Adrenergic Receptors and Promoting Dysbiosis that Contributes to Carcinogenesis. *Cancer Discov.* 12(4):1128–51
45. Briskin M, Winsor-Hines D, Shyjan A, Cochran N, Bloom S, et al. 1997. Human mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule-1 is preferentially expressed in intestinal tract and associated lymphoid tissue. *Am J Pathol.* 151(1):97–110
46. Choi Y, Lichterman JN, Coughlin LA, Poulides N, Li W, et al. 2023. Immune checkpoint blockade induces gut microbiota translocation that augments extraintestinal antitumor immunity. *Sci. Immunol.* 8(81):eabo2003
47. Li Y, Tinoco R, Elmén L, Segota I, Xian Y, et al. 2019. Gut microbiota dependent anti-tumor immunity restricts melanoma growth in *Rnf5*^{-/-} mice. *Nature Communications.* 10(1):
48. Le Chatelier E, Nielsen T, Qin J, Prifti E, Hildebrand F, et al. 2013. Richness of human gut microbiome correlates with metabolic markers. *Nature.* 500(7464):541–46
49. Gopalakrishnan V, Spencer CN, Nezi L, Reuben A, Andrews MC, et al. 2018. Gut microbiome modulates response to anti-PD-1 immunotherapy in melanoma patients. *Science*. 359(6371):97–103
50. Viaud S, Saccheri F, Mignot G, Yamazaki T, Daillere R, et al. 2013. The Intestinal Microbiota Modulates the Anticancer Immune Effects of Cyclophosphamide. *Science*. 342(6161):971–76
51. Vetizou M, Pitt JM, Daillere R, Lepage P, Waldschmitt N, et al. 2015. Anticancer immunotherapy by CTLA-4 blockade relies on the gut microbiota. *Science*. 350(6264):1079–84
52. Routy B, Gopalakrishnan V, Daillère R, Zitvogel L, Wargo JA, Kroemer G. 2018. The gut

microbiota influences anticancer immunosurveillance and general health. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*. 15(6):382–96

53. Tanoue T, Morita S, Plichta DR, Skelly AN, Suda W, et al. 2019. A defined commensal consortium elicits CD8 T cells and anti-cancer immunity. *Nature*. 565(7741):600–605
54. Matson V, Fessler J, Bao R, Chongsuwat T, Zha Y, et al. 2018. The commensal microbiome is associated with anti-PD-1 efficacy in metastatic melanoma patients. *Science*. 359(6371):104–8
55. Thomas AM, Fidelle M, Routy B, Kroemer G, Wargo JA, et al. 2023. Gut OncoMicrobiome Signatures (GOMS) as next-generation biomarkers for cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol*
56. McCulloch JA, Davar D, Rodrigues RR, Badger JH, Fang JR, et al. 2022. Intestinal microbiota signatures of clinical response and immune-related adverse events in melanoma patients treated with anti-PD-1. *Nat Med*. 28(3):545–56
57. Alves Costa Silva C, Piccinno G, Cerbone L, Iebba V, Colomba E, et al. 2022. 1452MO Longitudinal analysis reveals gut microbiota shift during standard therapies in metastatic renal cell carcinoma (mRCC). *Annals of Oncology*. 33:S1208
58. Park EM, Chelvanambi M, Bhutiani N, Kroemer G, Zitvogel L, Wargo JA. 2022. Targeting the gut and tumor microbiota in cancer. *Nat Med*. 28(4):690–703
59. Sivan A, Corrales L, Hubert N, Williams JB, Aquino-Michaels K, et al. 2015. Commensal *Bifidobacterium* promotes antitumor immunity and facilitates anti-PD-L1 efficacy. *Science*. 350(6264):1084–89
60. IHMS. <https://human-microbiome.org>
61. Cardona S, Eck A, Cassellas M, Gallart M, Alastrue C, et al. 2012. Storage conditions of intestinal microbiota matter in metagenomic analysis. *BMC Microbiol*. 12(1):158
62. Derosa L, Routy B, Thomas AM, Iebba V, Zalcman G, et al. 2022. Intestinal *Akkermansia muciniphila* predicts clinical response to PD-1 blockade in patients with advanced non-small-

cell lung cancer. *Nat Med.* 28(2):315–24

63. Frankel AE, Coughlin LA, Kim J, Froehlich TW, Xie Y, et al. 2017. Metagenomic Shotgun Sequencing and Unbiased Metabolomic Profiling Identify Specific Human Gut Microbiota and Metabolites Associated with Immune Checkpoint Therapy Efficacy in Melanoma Patients. *Neoplasia.* 19(10):848–55
64. Chaput N, Lepage P, Coutzac C, Soularue E, Le Roux K, et al. 2017. Baseline gut microbiota predicts clinical response and colitis in metastatic melanoma patients treated with ipilimumab. *Ann Oncol.* 28(6):1368–79
65. Alves Costa Silva C, Piccinno G, Suissa D, Bourgin M, Schreibelt G, et al. 2024. Influence of microbiota-associated metabolic reprogramming on clinical outcome in patients with melanoma from the randomized adjuvant dendritic cell-based MIND-DC trial. *Nat Commun.* 15(1):1633
66. Iadsee N, Chuaypen N, Techawiwattanaboon T, Jinato T, Patcharatrakul T, et al. 2023. Identification of a novel gut microbiota signature associated with colorectal cancer in Thai population. *Sci Rep.* 13(1):6702
67. Roberti MP, Yonekura S, Duong CPM, Picard M, Ferrere G, et al. 2020. Chemotherapy-induced ileal crypt apoptosis and the ileal microbiome shape immunosurveillance and prognosis of proximal colon cancer. *Nature Medicine.* 26(6):919–31
68. Almonte AA, Rangarajan H, Yip D, Fahrner AM. 2021. How does the gut microbiome influence immune checkpoint blockade therapy? *Immunol. Cell Biol.* 99(4):361–72
69. Lisa Derosa, Valerio Iebba, Carolina Alves Costa Silva, Gianmarco Piccinno, Guojun Wu, et al. Custom scoring based on ecological topology of gut microbiota associated with cancer immunotherapy outcome. *Cell.* in press:
70. Gupta VK, Kim M, Bakshi U, Cunningham KY, Davis JM, et al. 2020. A predictive index for health status using species-level gut microbiome profiling. *Nat Commun.* 11(1):4635
71. Nguyen SM, Tran HTT, Long J, Shrubsole MJ, Cai H, et al. 2024. Gut Microbiome of Patients

With Breast Cancer in Vietnam. *JCO Glob Oncol*, p. e2300234

72. Boulate D, Fidelle M, Caramella C, Issard J, Planché O, et al. 2022. Epidemiological Study to Assess the Prevalence of Lung Cancer in patients with smoking-associated atherosclerotic cardiovascular diseases: PREVALUNG study protocol. *BMJ Open*. 12(12):e067191
73. Ghosh P, Swanson L, Sayed IM, Mittal Y, Lim BB, et al. 2020. The stress polarity signaling (SPS) pathway serves as a marker and a target in the leaky gut barrier: implications in aging and cancer. *Life Science Alliance*. 3(3):
74. Aznar N, Patel A, Rohena CC, Dunkel Y, Joosen LP, et al. 2016. AMP-activated protein kinase fortifies epithelial tight junctions during energetic stress via its effector GIV/Girdin. *eLife*. 5:e20795
75. Shin N-R, Lee J-C, Lee H-Y, Kim M-S, Whon TW, et al. 2014. An increase in the Akkermansia spp. population induced by metformin treatment improves glucose homeostasis in diet-induced obese mice. *Gut*. 63(5):727–35
76. Takata F, Dohgu S, Matsumoto J, Machida T, Kaneshima S, et al. 2013. Metformin induces up-regulation of blood–brain barrier functions by activating AMP-activated protein kinase in rat brain microvascular endothelial cells. *Biochemical and Biophysical Research Communications*. 433(4):586–90
77. Ducarouge B, Pelissier-Rota M, Lainé M, Cristina N, Vachez Y, et al. 2013. CRF2 signaling is a novel regulator of cellular adhesion and migration in colorectal cancer cells. *PLoS One*. 8(11):e79335
78. Piton G, Capellier G. 2016. Biomarkers of gut barrier failure in the ICU. *Curr Opin Crit Care*. 22(2):152–60
79. Woo S-H, Lee S-H, Park J-W, Go D-M, Kim D-Y. 2019. Osteopontin Protects Colonic Mucosa from Dextran Sodium Sulfate-Induced Acute Colitis in Mice by Regulating Junctional Distribution of Occludin. *Dig Dis Sci*. 64(2):421–31
80. Tabung FK, Birmann BM, Epstein MM, Martínez-Maza O, Breen EC, et al. 2017. Influence

- of Dietary Patterns on Plasma Soluble CD14, a Surrogate Marker of Gut Barrier Dysfunction. *Current Developments in Nutrition*. 1(11):
81. Lewis JD. 2011. The utility of biomarkers in the diagnosis and therapy of inflammatory bowel disease. *Gastroenterology*. 140(6):1817-1826.e2
 82. Genua F, Holý P, Souček P, Liška V, Hughes DJ. 2023. Abstract 5544: Association of circulating markers of gut barrier damage and inflammation with colorectal neoplasia stage. *Cancer Research*. 83(7_Supplement):5544
 83. Keane JM, Las Heras V, Pinheiro J, FitzGerald JA, Núñez-Sánchez MA, et al. 2023. Akkermansia muciniphila reduces susceptibility to Listeria monocytogenes infection in mice fed a high-fat diet. *Gut Microbes*. 15(1):2229948
 84. Nasiri G, Azimirad M, Goudarzi H, Amirkamali S, Yadegar A, et al. 2023. The inhibitory effects of live and UV-killed Akkermansia muciniphila and its derivatives on cytotoxicity and inflammatory response induced by Clostridioides difficile RT001 in vitro. *Int Microbiol*
 85. Petrick JL, Florio AA, Zen J, Wang Y, Gewirtz AT, et al. 2023. Biomarkers of gut barrier dysfunction and risk of hepatocellular carcinoma in the REVEAL-HBV and REVEAL-HCV cohort studies. *International Journal of Cancer*. 153(1):44–53
 86. Chen L, Reynolds C, David R, Peace Brewer A. 2020. Development of an Index Score for Intestinal Inflammation-Associated Dysbiosis Using Real-World Stool Test Results. *Dig Dis Sci*. 65(4):1111–24
 87. Sachpekidis C, Stein-Thoeringer CK, Kopp-Schneider A, Weru V, Dimitrakopoulou-Strauss A, Hassel JC. 2023. Can physiologic colonic [18F]FDG uptake in PET/CT imaging predict response to immunotherapy in metastatic melanoma? *Eur J Nucl Med Mol Imaging*. 50(12):3709–22
 88. Sorribas M, Jakob MO, Yilmaz B, Li H, Stutz D, et al. 2019. FXR modulates the gut-vascular barrier by regulating the entry sites for bacterial translocation in experimental cirrhosis. *J Hepatol*. 71(6):1126–40

89. Stan RV, Tse D, Deharvengt SJ, Smits NC, Xu Y, et al. 2012. The Diaphragms of Fenestrated Endothelia: Gatekeepers of Vascular Permeability and Blood Composition. *Developmental Cell*. 23(6):1203–18
90. Bertocchi A, Carloni S, Ravenda PS, Bertalot G, Spadoni I, et al. 2021. Gut vascular barrier impairment leads to intestinal bacteria dissemination and colorectal cancer metastasis to liver. *Cancer Cell*. 39(5):708-724.e11
91. Silva CAC, Fidelle M, Birebent R, Dalban C, Zoppi S, et al. 2023. Serum soluble MAdCAM-1: A new biomarker for cancer immunotherapy. *JCO*. 41(16_suppl):4548–4548
92. Abdel Sater AH, Bouferraa Y, Amhaz G, Haibe Y, Shamseddine A. 2022. From Tumor Cells to Endothelium and Gut Microbiome: A Complex Interaction Favoring the Metastasis Cascade. *Front. Oncol*. 12:
93. Banerjee S, Wei Z, Tian T, Bose D, Shih NNC, et al. 2021. Prognostic correlations with the microbiome of breast cancer subtypes. *Cell Death Dis*. 12(9):831
94. Dohlman AB, Klug J, Mesko M, Gao IH, Lipkin SM, et al. 2022. A pan-cancer mycobiome analysis reveals fungal involvement in gastrointestinal and lung tumors. *Cell*. 185(20):3807-3822.e12
95. Goubet A-G. 2023. Could the tumor-associated microbiota be the new multi-faceted player in the tumor microenvironment? *Front. Oncol*. 13:1185163
96. Narunsky-Haziza L, Sepich-Poore GD, Livyatan I, Asraf O, Martino C, et al. 2022. Pan-cancer analyses reveal cancer-type-specific fungal ecologies and bacteriome interactions. *Cell*. 185(20):3789-3806.e17
97. Tzeng A, Sangwan N, Jia M, Liu C-C, Keslar KS, et al. 2021. Human breast microbiome correlates with prognostic features and immunological signatures in breast cancer. *Genome Med*. 13(1):60
98. Nejman D, Livyatan I, Fuks G, Gavert N, Zwang Y, et al. 2020. The human tumor microbiome is composed of tumor type–specific intracellular bacteria. *Science*. 368(6494):973–80

99. Farias A, Soto A, Puttur F, Goldin CJ, Sosa S, et al. 2021. A TLR4 agonist improves immune checkpoint blockade treatment by increasing the ratio of effector to regulatory cells within the tumor microenvironment. *Sci Rep.* 11(1):15406
100. Sharma N, Vacher J, Allison JP. 2019. TLR1/2 ligand enhances antitumor efficacy of CTLA-4 blockade by increasing intratumoral Treg depletion. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* 116(21):10453–62
101. Postow MA, Sidlow R, Hellmann MD. 2018. Immune-Related Adverse Events Associated with Immune Checkpoint Blockade. *N Engl J Med.* 378(2):158–68
102. Dougan M. 2023. Gastrointestinal mucosal toxicities from immune checkpoint inhibitors: Current understanding and future directions. *Immunological Reviews.* 318(1):11–21
103. Soularue E, Lepage P, Colombel JF, Coutzac C, Faleck D, et al. 2018. Enterocolitis due to immune checkpoint inhibitors: a systematic review. *Gut.* 67(11):2056–67
104. Ye W, Olsson-Brown A, Watson RA, Cheung VTF, Morgan RD, et al. 2021. Checkpoint-blocker-induced autoimmunity is associated with favourable outcome in metastatic melanoma and distinct T-cell expression profiles. *Br J Cancer.* 124(10):1661–69
105. Naghavian R, Faigle W, Oldrati P, Wang J, Toussaint NC, et al. 2023. Microbial peptides activate tumour-infiltrating lymphocytes in glioblastoma. *Nature.* 617(7962):807–17
106. Ragone C, Manolio C, Mauriello A, Cavalluzzo B, Buonaguro FM, et al. 2022. Molecular mimicry between tumor associated antigens and microbiota-derived epitopes. *J Transl Med.* 20(1):316
107. Zitvogel L, Kroemer G. 2022. Cross-reactivity between microbial and tumor antigens. *Current Opinion in Immunology.* 75:102171
108. Fluckiger A, Daillère R, Sassi M, Sixt BS, Liu P, et al. 2020. Cross-reactivity between tumor MHC class I-restricted antigens and an enterococcal bacteriophage. *Science.* 369(6506):936–42
109. Kalaora S, Nagler A, Nejman D, Alon M, Barbolin C, et al. 2021. Identification of bacteria-

derived HLA-bound peptides in melanoma. *Nature*. 592(7852):138–43

110. Cui C, Wang J, Fagerberg E, Chen P-M, Connolly KA, et al. 2021. Neoantigen-driven B cell and CD4 T follicular helper cell collaboration promotes anti-tumor CD8 T cell responses. *Cell*. 184(25):6101-6118.e13
111. Ng KW, Boumelha J, Enfield KSS, Almagro J, Cha H, et al. 2023. Antibodies against endogenous retroviruses promote lung cancer immunotherapy. *Nature*. 616(7957):563–73
112. Goubet A-G, Lordello L, Alves Costa Silva C, Peguillet I, Gazzano M, et al. 2022. Escherichia coli-Specific CXCL13-Producing TFH Are Associated with Clinical Efficacy of Neoadjuvant PD-1 Blockade against Muscle-Invasive Bladder Cancer. *Cancer Discov*. 12(10):2280–2307
113. Jones GW, Hill DG, Jones SA. 2016. Understanding Immune Cells in Tertiary Lymphoid Organ Development: It Is All Starting to Come Together. *Front. Immunol*. 7:
114. Sautès-Fridman C, Lawand M, Giraldo NA, Kaplon H, Germain C, et al. 2016. Tertiary Lymphoid Structures in Cancers: Prognostic Value, Regulation, and Manipulation for Therapeutic Intervention. *Front. Immunol*. 7:
115. Chen YE, Bousbaine D, Veinbachs A, Atabakhsh K, Dimas A, et al. 2023. Engineered skin bacteria induce antitumor T cell responses against melanoma. *Science*. 380(6641):203–10
116. Wang M, Rousseau B, Qiu K, Huang G, Zhang Y, et al. 2023. Killing tumor-associated bacteria with a liposomal antibiotic generates neoantigens that induce anti-tumor immune responses. *Nat Biotechnol*
117. Kanehisa M, Goto S. 2000. KEGG: kyoto encyclopedia of genes and genomes. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 28(1):27–30
118. Koh A, De Vadder F, Kovatcheva-Datchary P, Bäckhed F. 2016. From Dietary Fiber to Host Physiology: Short-Chain Fatty Acids as Key Bacterial Metabolites. *Cell*. 165(6):1332–45
119. Luu M, Riester Z, Baldrich A, Reichardt N, Yuille S, et al. 2021. Microbial short-chain fatty acids modulate CD8+ T cell responses and improve adoptive immunotherapy for cancer. *Nat Commun*. 12(1):4077

120. Thiele Orberg E, Meedt E, Hiergeist A, Xue J, Heinrich P, et al. 2024. Bacteria and bacteriophage consortia are associated with protective intestinal metabolites in patients receiving stem cell transplantation. *Nat Cancer*. 5(1):187–208
121. Lindner S, Miltiadous O, Ramos RJF, Paredes J, Kousa AI, et al. 2024. Altered microbial bile acid metabolism exacerbates T cell-driven inflammation during graft-versus-host disease. *Nat Microbiol*. 9(3):614–30
122. Gao RY, Shearn CT, Orlicky DJ, Battista KD, Alexeev EE, et al. 2021. Bile acids modulate colonic MAdCAM-1 expression in a murine model of combined cholestasis and colitis. *Mucosal Immunol*. 14(2):479–90
123. Wang F, Yu T, Huang G, Cai D, Liang X, et al. 2015. Gut Microbiota Community and Its Assembly Associated with Age and Diet in Chinese Centenarians. *J Microbiol Biotechnol*. 25(8):1195–1204
124. Ma C, Han M, Heinrich B, Fu Q, Zhang Q, et al. 2018. Gut microbiome-mediated bile acid metabolism regulates liver cancer via NKT cells. *Science*. 360(6391):eaan5931
125. Girisa S, Henamayee S, Parama D, Rana V, Dutta U, Kunnumakkara AB. 2021. Targeting Farnesoid X receptor (FXR) for developing novel therapeutics against cancer. *Mol Biomed*. 2(1):21
126. Tian H, Gui Y, Wei Y, Shang B, Sun J, et al. 2021. Z-guggulsterone induces PD-L1 upregulation partly mediated by FXR, Akt and Erk1/2 signaling pathways in non-small cell lung cancer. *International Immunopharmacology*. 93:107395
127. Steed AL, Christophi GP, Kaiko GE, Sun L, Goodwin VM, et al. 2017. The microbial metabolite desaminotyrosine protects from influenza through type I interferon. *Science*. 357(6350):498–502
128. Joachim L, Götttert S, Sax A, Steiger K, Neuhaus K, et al. 2023. The microbial metabolite desaminotyrosine enhances T-cell priming and cancer immunotherapy with immune checkpoint inhibitors. *eBioMedicine*. 97:104834

129. Thiele Orberg E, Göttert S, Hiergeist A, Meedt E, Kleigrewe K, et al. 2021. Microbial-Derived Metabolites Induce Epithelial Recovery Via the Sting Pathway in Mice and Men and Protect from Graft-Versus-Host Disease. *Blood*. 138(Supplement 1):87–87
130. Bhandari MP, Polaka I, Vangravs R, Mezmale L, Veliks V, et al. 2023. Volatile Markers for Cancer in Exhaled Breath—Could They Be the Signature of the Gut Microbiota? *Molecules*. 28(8):3488
131. Hoffmann DE, Von Rosenvinge EC, Roghmann M-C, Palumbo FB, McDonald D, Ravel J. 2024. The DTC microbiome testing industry needs more regulation. *Science*. 383(6688):1176–79
132. Santiago A, Panda S, Mengels G, Martinez X, Azpiroz F, et al. 2014. Processing faecal samples: a step forward for standards in microbial community analysis. *BMC Microbiol*. 14(1):112
133. *Final Report Summary - METABOLOMICSSTANDARD (Metabolomics: defining the standards for sample preparation of small molecules) / FP7*. CORDIS | European Commission. <https://cordis.europa.eu>
134. García-Cárdenas JM, Indacochea A, Pesantez-Coronel D, Terán-Navas M, Aleaga A, et al. 2024. Toward Equitable Precision Oncology: Monitoring Racial and Ethnic Inclusion in Genomics and Clinical Trials. *JCO Precis Oncol*, p. e2300398
135. The Lancet. 2024. Cancer research equity: innovations for the many, not the few. *The Lancet*. 403(10425):409
136. Liu Z, De Vries B, Gerritsen J, Smidt H, Zoetendal EG. 2020. Microbiome-based stratification to guide dietary interventions to improve human health. *Nutrition Research*. 82:1–10
137. Lee KA, Thomas AM, Bolte LA, Björk JR, de Ruijter LK, et al. 2022. Cross-cohort gut microbiome associations with immune checkpoint inhibitor response in advanced melanoma. *Nat Med*. 28(3):535–44
138. Golčić M, Simetić L, Herceg D, Blažičević K, Kenđel Jovanović G, et al. 2023. Analysis of

the Gut Microbiome and Dietary Habits in Metastatic Melanoma Patients with a Complete and Sustained Response to Immunotherapy. *Cancers*. 15(11):3052

139. Dora D, Ligeti B, Kovacs T, Revisnyei P, Galffy G, et al. 2023. Non-small cell lung cancer patients treated with Anti-PD1 immunotherapy show distinct microbial signatures and metabolic pathways according to progression-free survival and PD-L1 status. *OncImmunity*. 12(1):2204746
140. Chau J, Yadav M, Liu B, Furqan M, Dai Q, et al. 2021. Prospective correlation between the patient microbiome with response to and development of immune-mediated adverse effects to immunotherapy in lung cancer. *BMC Cancer*. 21(1):808
141. Xu L, Ma Y, Fang C, Peng Z, Gao F, et al. 2022. Genomic and microbial factors affect the prognosis of anti-pd-1 immunotherapy in nasopharyngeal carcinoma. *Front. Oncol*. 12:953884
142. Spiliopoulou P, Rooney A, Genta S, Kulikova M, Wang BX, et al. 2023. Intestinal microbiome characterization in immune checkpoint inhibition (ICI) resistant disease. *JCO*. 41(16_suppl):2515–2515

Acknowledgements

We would like to particularly thank the patients who participate in the ClinicObiome medical scientific program and all the research group at the Gustave Roussy Cancer Campus who are involved in the program execution. We especially want to thank Pierre Ly, Cassandra Thelemaque, Marie Xiberras, Mathias Marques, Eugénie Pizzatto, Caroline Flament, Maria Semedo de Brito and Nathalie Malherbe. CACS, MF, LD and LZ are supported by the SEERAVE Foundation. CACS and LZ are supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program No 964590 (project acronym: IHMCSA, project entitled International Human Microbiome Coordination and Support Action). LZ is supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101095604 (project acronym: PREVALUNG-EU, project title: Personalized lung cancer risk assessment leading to stratified Interception), the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 825410 (ONCOBIOME project), Institut National du Cancer (INCa), ANR Ileobiome - 19-CE15-0029-01, ANR RHU5 "ANR-21-5 RHUS-0017" IMMUNOLIFE", MAdCAM INCA_ 16698, Ligue contre le cancer, the LabEx Immuno-Oncology (ANR-18-IDEX-0001), la direction generale de l'offre de soins (DGOS), Université Paris-Saclay, PACRI network, Ligue contre le Cancer (équipes labellisées, Program "Equipe labellisée LIGUE"; no. EL2016.LNCC (VT/PLP)); Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR) –Projets blancs; ANR under the frame of E-Rare-2, the ERA-Net for Research on Rare Diseases; AMMICa US23/CNRS UMS3655; Association pour la recherche sur le cancer (ARC); Association "Le Cancer du Sein, Parlons-en!"; Cancéropôle Ile-de-France; Chancellerie des

universités de Paris (Legs Poix), Fondation pour la Recherche Médicale (FRM); a donation by Elior; European Research Area Network on Cardiovascular Diseases (ERA-CVD, MINOTAUR); Gustave Roussy Odyssey, Fondation Carrefour; INCa; Inserm (HTE); Institut Universitaire de France; LeDucq Foundation; and the SIRIC Cancer Research and Personalized Medicine (CARPEM). CACS was supported by MSD Avenir. The funders had no role in the writing of the review, or in the decision to publish it.

Declaration of interests

LZ is founder of everImmune and its SAB President. LD is an everImmune SAB member. LZ received a research contract from Kaleido, 9 meters/Innovate Pharma and is currently sponsored by Pileje.

Figure 1. The microbiota clinic: an overview of a two-step approach for microbiome risk stratification in clinical care.

A. Clinical evaluation must assess host and environment factors for microbiota risk stratification. These factors could include the patient's age, lifestyle (BMI, physical activity, diet, etc.), environmental factors, and co-medications. Each could significantly impact gut microbiota composition and, consequently, alter their responsiveness to therapy. **B.** Biomarkers for gut dysbiosis will be identified from blood and stool samples using metagenomics, spectrometry, flow cytometry, and ELISA. The information they provide can be synergized with host and environmental factors to help caregivers make better-informed decisions about who will benefit most from immunotherapy. Body mass index (BMI); Desaminotyrosine (DAT); Proton pump inhibitors (PPI); Lipopolysaccharide (LPS); Lipopolysaccharide-binding protein (LBP); Short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs); Soluble CD14 (sCD14); Soluble Mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule 1 (sMAdCAM-1); Soluble ST2 (sST2); Tertiary lymphoid structures (TLS). Created with BioRender.com.

Figure 2. Gut microbiota-based algorithm for patient identification, diagnosis and classification of gut dysbiosis for personalized microbiota-centered intervention.

A. Personalized approaches based on gut-related biomarkers stratification of gut dysbiosis. **B.** Gut-related biomarkers can be used to monitor the status of gut fitness during anticancer treatment and microbiota-centered interventions (assessing pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics). *Akkermansia*: *Akk*; Soluble CD14 (sCD14); Soluble Mucosal addressin cell adhesion molecule 1 (sMAdCAM-1); Soluble ST2 (sST2). Created with BioRender.com.

Microbiota risk stratification

(A) Assess host and environmental factors

Age Performance status Physical activity Family history	Body composition BMI, muscle mass, total and visceral fat Environment Rural / City Stress Exposure	Comedications Antibiotics PPI Depressant drugs Laxatives Probiotics Antidiabetic drugs (i.e. metformin)	Dietary habits Vegetarian Mediterranean Red meat Processed food Composition: fiber (g/day), protein (source), fat
--	---	--	--

Diagnosis of dysbiosis

(B) Assess gut fitness

Sample collection

Multi-omics signatures

Taxonomy

Richness
Microbial species
TOPOSCORE
Exfoliome

Metabolites

SCFAs, bile acids, DAT,
kynurenine,
tryptophan, inosine

Lymphocytes

Anti-microbial
IgA and IgG titers,
TLS (CCL19, CXCL13)

Gut inflammation

Calprotectin (S100A9),
LPS/LPB, CRP, cytokines
(IL-6, TNF- α)

Barrier Integrity

sST2, sCD14

Gut-vascular barrier

sMAdCAM-1

**Metagenomics
shotgun sequencing**

**Liquid and gas
mass spectrometry**

Flow cytometry

ELISA

(A) Personalized approaches

(B) Monitoring

